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Careers in VET

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Abstract

Further education and training provision is crucial to develop a sustainable, self-determined career, but also to continuously build knowledge and skills that allow an active and a sustainable participation at work. We have a closer look at the planning and engagement in informal, or formal further education and training after having finished initial VET. We focus on contextual factors which might have an influence of becoming engaged in further education. First, we ask for the effect of the value an individual assigns to further education and the availability of information on planning and becoming engaged in further education. Such values play a crucial role in career decisions and was shown in motivational theories of educational choices as well as the availability of information leading to informed career decisions. Second, we ask for predictors of the value and the information available by looking at individual and work-related factors. Specifically, we test the hypothesis that an individual's protean career orientation, learning opportunities and the embeddedness in the work-group are correlated with the value and the available information. We can show differential effects of these factors on planning and engagement in further education. Our data stemmed from two waves of a multi-cohort longitudinal questionnaire-based survey on educational decisions and educational pathways (BEN), running from 2012 to 2016 in the German part of Switzerland. We discuss the results considering the consistent gendered educational and professional pathways by showing that individual and workplace factors have gender-specific effects on the value of further education, the information available and consequently on the planning and engagement in further education. It is crucial to have a closer look at different processes and pathways to further education that seem to replicate structures in which men strive for further education in sake of advancing their career and women stick to the work team if it is supportive postpone the planning of further education.

Keywords

career planning, engagement, gender, decision process

1 Careers in VET

Further and continuing education serves many goals. It lays the grounds for a satisfying individual career (Price & Reichert, 2017); in many countries, policy interventions aim at enabling continuing learning pathways (Hooley, 2014); societal or technological changes ask for

continuous engagement in learning in the workplace (Noe et al., 2014). Despite the high importance of further education, many young people do no longer invest in their educational career once they have acquired their job-entry diploma and once they have become employed. Generally, people leaving the "learning pathway" (Biemans et al., 2018) are at a higher risk to invest in the long term less in their continuing education and eventually to cease further education activities.

After having completed initial vocational education and training, most young people start working either in their training company or another company. In the foreground is the work in the company, after a long period of training. They take the decision to take up further education against this background. After having finished initial vocational education and training, it is expected and legitimate first to focus on the job. But in the long-term, the job-entrants should start investing in their further education. The question is what motivates young people at work to get back on a learning pathway and become engaged in further education (Nägele & Stalder, 2019).

In this paper, we focus on an individual's motivation for attending further formal education on the tertiary level or in continuous education after having completed initial vocational education and training on the upper secondary level. Following motivational models of educational choices, the value given to further education is an essential driver in developing the attitude to plan and attend further education (Wigfield et al., 2017). Values can be seen as an external factor in terms of the social cognitive career theory (Lent & Brown, 2020). Values allow people to take a decision to follow a specific goal which is in conflict to another goal (Hofer et al., 2007). This is an important process if it comes to a decision on whether to remain working and earning money versus becoming engaged in a further education which reduces in the short term the income or hampers resources for the family or other individual activities. The knowledge about further educational options helps to structure and differentiate the planning and also to foresee the consequences of decisions, and information can help to overcome decision biases (Greenhaus & Powell, 2012). A lack of information can hinder an individual to enter a career choice process or to take a decision (Kulcsár et al., 2020). We hypothesise that the interplay of the value of further education and the availability of information will increase the likelihood of planning further education and at a later point in time also of becoming engaged in further education.

Additionally, we ask what factors might influence the value and availability of information. Several factors are discussed that might point the path to further education, such as sociodemographic, psychological, or organisational aspects (Kyndt & Baert, 2013). In our study, first, we highlight the role of individual and job-related factors in predicting the value of further education and in adding to the availability of information. More specifically, we have a look at the protean career orientation of an individual (Hall, 2004). An individual with a protean career orientation is self-directed and compared to an individual that relies on the organisation to advance one's career (Hall et al., 2018). These people take their career decisions make their decisions independently. Second, we are looking at the work design. A work situation in which a person can use and develop knowledge and skills will more likely stimulate the wish to develop competences and to invest further education and training as work becomes more meaningful (Hackman & Oldham, 1975). A good job-design is a resource that can stimulate personal growth and development (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). More specifically, we look at the vital role of learning opportunities at work. Thirdly, we will have a look at the role of the team in advancing an individual's educational career. Work teams are an essential resource for individuals, also if it comes to the development of competences within the team. Organisations rely on teamwork (Salas, 2005). Team cohesion and development opportunities within the team can also hinder the planning of further external education.

We hypothesise that a protean career orientation and learning opportunities at work will have a positive impact on the values and the availability of information. The effect a team can have

can either be positive or negative, as it is not completely clear whether a supportive team fosters or hinders the planning of further education. Hence, we formulate this hypothesis without determining the direction of the effect.

In Switzerland, vocational and educational pathways often differ between women and men. Vocational and professional pathways are still heavily gendered (SKBF, 2018). This fact is mirrored in the data of the Federal Statistical Office (<https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/de/home.html>). We expect that the protean career orientation, the learning opportunities and social support by the team have a gender-specific effect on the value of further education and the availability of information. The conceptual model is given in Figure .

Figure 1

Conceptual model planning and engagement in further education

2 Methods

Our data stemmed from two waves of a multi-cohort longitudinal questionnaire-based survey on educational decisions and educational pathways (BEN), running from 2012 to 2016 in the German part of Switzerland (Neuenschwander et al., 2018). The participants were either recruited in 2012 at vocational schools (cohort one), by sending out letters to employers, asking them to name collaborators to participate in the study or by directly sending out letters to potential participants (cohort two). The selected sample for the analysis in this paper consisted of individuals who took part in 2014 (wave 1) and 2016 (wave 2). We selected those 634 people from the sample who were in 2014 working and not engaged in education and training; the age limit was set to 35 years.

Wave 1: Planning. Participants were asked about their plans to attend further education with a single item with the answer options 1 "no plans", 2 "vague plans" to 3 "specific plans" (Neuenschwander et al., 2018), mean = 1.63; standard deviation = .74, $N = 641$, min = 1, max = 2, and median = 1.00. **Availability of information.** Participants were asked on how good they were informed about their options to attend further education. Four items asked how informed the participants were on offers in further education (Neuenschwander et al., 2018), for example 'I have a good overview of offers in further education and training'. The response scale ranged from 1 'not at all' to 6 'completely', Cronbach's alpha = .84, mean = 3.96; standard deviation = .96, $N = 643$, min = 1, max = 6, and median = 4.00. **Value of further education.** The value given to further formal education was measured according to Wigfield et al. (2017) with three items. 'I consider further education and training for me as... a) useful, b) important, c) attractive'. The response scale ranged from 1 'not at all true' to 6 'completely true', Cronbach's alpha = .84, mean = 4.89, standard deviation = .91, $N = 643$, min = 1, max = 6, and median = 5.00. **Protean career orientation** was measured with three items (Briscoe et al., 2006). Cronbach's alpha = .77, mean = 4.26, standard deviation = .58, $N = 643$, min = 1, max = 5, and median = 4.33. **Learning opportunities** at work was assessed with three items (Prümper et al., 1995), for example, 'I can learn a lot of new things at work' based on the skill variety at work. The response

scale ranged from 1 'not at all' to 5 'completely', Cronbach's alpha = .75, mean = 3.87; standard deviation = .80, $N = 634$, min = 1, max = 5, and median = 4.00. *Social support* was assessed with three items (Prümper et al., 1995), for example, 'I can count on my colleagues when it gets difficult at work'. The response scale ranged from 1 'not at all' to 5 'completely', Cronbach's alpha = .77, mean = 4.06, standard deviation = .78, $N = 641$, min = 1, max = 5, and median = 4.00.

Wave 2: Engagement in further education. Some of the participants had no plans or were still planning their further education, whereas others were attending or had even completed further education since 2014. To define the outcome variable that reflects the engagement in further education, a compound variable was built, based on the following information. First, people were asked in a multiple response item whether they were employed or in further education. Second, in a single item participants were asked about their plans to attend further education with the answer options 1 "no plans", 2 "vague plans" to 3 "specific plans" (Neuenschwander et al., 2018). Third, participants were asked to list all further education that they attended during the last years. The resulting variable has three levels 1 "no engagement", 2 "little engagement", 3 "full engagement", mean = 1.91; standard deviation = .88, $N = 643$, min = 1, max = 3, and median = 2.

3 Results

Analysis with manifest variables were run, separately for women and men, see Figure 2, using JASP (JASP, 2020).

For men, the effect of planning on engagement was significant, .36, $p < .01$. There were significant effects of the value of further education, .28, $p < .01$, and the availability of information, .20, $p < .01$ on planning. There was no direct effect of the availability of information, .10, $p = .09$ and no direct effect of the values, .04, $p = .51$ on engagement. For women, we find a significant effect of planning on engagement, .28, $p < .01$. There are significant effects of the value of further education, .28, $p < .01$, and the availability of information, .16, $p < .01$ on planning. There is no direct effect from information on engagement, .02, $p = .63$, but a direct effect of value, .16, $p < .01$. This results replicate previous findings showing that the value of further education and the available information lead to planning which later results in engagement in further education. The results show also that the value of further education is more critical for the motivation to follow further education for women than for men. For men, it is the planning that counts. It seems that men can implement their plans to pursue further education more consistently than women. Based on the data available, we can only guess about possible reasons. Men engage in further education because they have planned it, women, because they have planned it and because it is of a high value. The crucial differences in the two models become evident by looking at protean career, learning opportunities and social support as predictors of value of further education and information available. We found different results for men and women. For men, the availability information was only predicted by protean career, .32, $p < .01$ and value only by protean career, .16, $p = .04$. Neither learning opportunities nor social support predicted value availability of information. In men, protean carer orientation is positively related to planning and engagement, based on more information and higher values attributed to further education. For men, we find no effect of workplace factors nor of the social support in the team. The picture is different for women. Information was predicted by learning opportunities, .20, $p < .01$ and negatively by social support, -.17, $p < .01$; value is predicted by protean career, .15, $p < .01$ and negatively by social support, -.10, $p = .04$. In women protean career orientation is a good predictor of the value of further education, positive learning opportunities are positively related to the availability of information, and positive social support hinders information seeking, as it is negatively related to it.

We see two very distinct patterns for men and women on how information and value relate to protean career orientation, learning opportunities and social support at work. Men seem to

plan their career based on their mindset that they need to design their career and that it is their responsibility. Learning opportunities additionally drive women at work. If they work in a supportive work environment, they seem to become less interested in information about further education, and they value further education lower.

Figure 2

Path models for women and men – engagement in further education

female

male

4 Discussion

We can show that individual factors, the job-design and work-related social factors play a role in planning and becoming engaged in further education. The process goes through stimulating information seeking and through the value given to further education.

The results presented are based on data from young working people after having finished initial vocational education and training. We are, in a way puzzled by the results, as it seems to confirm many stereotypes that come to mind. Are young men in Switzerland driven to become engaged in further education based on their career thinking and women by the value they assign to further education? It would be interesting to have a closer look at the underlying processes. Based on the data available, we can only take notice that there are differences and that women rely besides on the values more on workplace factors in designing their further educational pathway, which leads to the question on employers' options to promote women's educational careers more strongly than for men.

Implication for theory. The process in becoming engaged in further education is different for women and men and social support, which is generally seen as positive at the workplace, can hurt the availability of information on further education. As values help people to handle conflicting goals their role in the decision process of women and man needs to get closer attention {Hofer et al., 2007, #70076}. It might well be that women rely more on social support and that they are satisfied with the situation. Therefore, the value of further education becomes more

important as it must compete against e.g., family values. Men become motivated to follow further education if it fits their thinking of designing their professional career. Women become engaged if they assign value to further education. Women and men seem to pursue different objectives when planning further education.

Implications for practice. The result shows that we need to promote learning pathways and educational careers of women and men differently. Based on our findings, a woman's path to further can be promoted supporting their planning and additionally help them to highlight that further education is of high value. Men, on the other hand, can be triggered by a prospect that they can follow their career.

Limitations. In this paper, first results are presented. This paper presents preliminary results, based on manifest constructs. It is planned to refine the analyses running the model with latent variables.

Conclusion. If we want to foster career of women and men having completed initial vocational education and training, we need to take into account that different factors trigger the planning of and engagement in further education. Whereas men seem to rely on information and a strong protean career orientation, women rely also on their workgroup and learning opportunities at the workplace. One size of measures does not fit all!

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Biographical notes

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